

Culture Confirmed Biliary Pathogens and Antimicrobial Resistance in Acute Cholecystitis: A Systematic Review

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Introduction

Inadequate response to empiric antibiotic therapy is becoming a major concern in patients with acute cholecystitis, mainly due to the increasing prevalence of resistant bacterial species. Moreover, pathogen distribution and resistance rates can vary between patients. Hence, this systematic review aimed to synthesize available evidence on culture-confirmed biliary pathogens and their antimicrobial resistance patterns in patients with acute cholecystitis.

Materials and Methods

The databases PubMed, Scopus, and Embase were systematically searched to identify relevant records reporting bile culture results and antibiotic susceptibility in patients with acute cholecystitis. Data on bacterial isolates and antibiotic resistance patterns were extracted. Pathogen prevalence patterns and resistance rates were summarized using descriptive statistics.

Results

Fifteen observational studies reporting microbial compositions of bile samples were included in the synthesis of this review. The most common organisms were *E. coli* (35.7%), *Klebsiella* spp. (19.3%), *Enterococcus* spp. (16.4%), and *Enterobacter* spp. (7.9%). For resistance, the main pooled findings were ESBL-producing gram-negative isolates at 10.0% and vancomycin-resistant/non-susceptible *Enterococcus* spp. at 8.2%. Various species presented resistance to fluoroquinolones as well.

Conclusion

Bacterial infections in acute cholecystitis are predominantly caused by Gram-negative species, particularly *E. coli* and *Klebsiella* spp. The high prevalence of ESBL-producing species indicates the need for more frequent local microbiological surveillance and the adaptation of culture-guided antibiotic therapy as a strategy for better therapeutic results. Moreover, local resistance patterns should guide empiric antibiotic selection and reinforce culture-guided antibiotic therapy where indicated.

Keywords

Acute cholecystitis, antibiotic resistance